

A. Supplementary maps for NGC 4030

Fig. 1. σ_* maps of NGC 4030 obtained with pPXF with IUS templates by fitting – panel a) 6 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features and emission-lines simultaneously, on nebular-continuum subtracted spectra; panel b) 6 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features while masking emission-lines, on nebular-continuum subtracted spectra; panel c) 4 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features and emission-lines simultaneously, on nebular-continuum subtracted spectra; panel d) 4 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features while masking emission-lines, on nebular-continuum subtracted spectra; panel e) 4 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features and emission-lines simultaneously, without subtracting the nebular-continuum; panel f) 4 kinematic moments, stellar absorption features while masking emission-lines, without subtracting the nebular-continuum. Results utilising the MILES templates are equivalent. The σ_* spiral features are evident in all cases.

In this work, contribution of the nebular continuum is modelled and subtracted prior to fitting with pPXF. However, typical star-forming galaxies such as NGC 4030, with $\text{EWH}(\alpha) < 200 \text{ \AA}$, display weak nebular emission, and its correction has a small effect, which can be appreciated by comparing the the upper with the lower panels of Fig. 1). The methodology adopted for the decontamination of the spectra is provided below:

- a) $\text{H}\alpha$ and $\text{H}\beta$ fluxes are measured, allowing for the determination of intrinsic V-band extinction via the Balmer decrement;
- b) using a nebular continuum SED template as input, corresponding to standard conditions (electron temperature of 10.000 K and electron density of 100 cm^3), and computed following standard prescriptions (e.g., Krueger, Fritze-v. Alvensleben, & Loose 1995; Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange 1997):
 - b1) the nebular continuum SED template is subjected to intrinsic extinction (based on the observed $\text{H}\alpha/\text{H}\beta$ ratio);
 - b2) the modelled nebular continuum, to be subtracted to the observed spectra, is finally obtained by scaling the extinguished nebular continuum SED to the observed (therefore also extinguished) $\text{H}\alpha$ flux.

Fig. 2. Fitting elliptical isophotes to the MUSE integrated light within 6390 – 6490 Å. Best-fitting ellipses are overlaid, shown alongside the model and residuals. These ellipses define the geometry used for extracting the radial profiles of the varied physical quantities assessed in this study.

Fig. 3. Panel a presents the baseline-subtracted $H\alpha$ map of NGC 4030, with the corresponding radial profiles displayed in panel b. Panel c shows the $EW(H\alpha)$ map derived from FADO, i.e., without subtraction of the best-fitting underlying model, in contrast to previous maps. Panel d showcases the radial profiles of $EW(H\alpha)$. Consistent with previous figures, the spiral arms are superimposed in the maps, and the radial profiles evaluate regions inside and outside the spiral arms, as well as across the entire map.

Fig. 4. Modelling and subtraction of the underlying substructure of HST F450W photometry image with KINEMETRY.

Fig. 5. Modelling and subtraction of the underlying σ_* substructure with KINEMETRY.

Fig. 6. Modelling and subtraction of the underlying $\tau_{*,L}$ substructure assessed by FADO with KINEMETRY.

Fig. 7. Modelling and subtraction of the underlying $H\alpha$ substructure with KINEMETRY.